

Revolutionising Performance: Public Perception of How Fintech is Transforming Service Delivery in Public Institutions in Greater Amman Municipality

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Abstract

Background: The increasing digitalisation of the financial sector has positioned Financial Technology (FinTech) as a critical vector for public sector transformation. This work is motivated by the necessity to analyse how integrating FinTech solutions can significantly enhance both the accessibility and operational efficiency of services delivered by government institutions.

Objective: The main objective is to assess the impact of financial technology on public institutions, particularly in terms of user satisfaction, operational competence, and service delivery.

Methodology: This study employed a quantitative, cross-sectional survey design. Data were collected via a self-administered questionnaire distributed to 326 employees to examine the relationship between institutional FinTech adoption and organisational performance. The analysis involved descriptive statistics to characterise the sample and key variables, followed by inferential analysis to test the hypothesised relationships empirically.

Results: Research shows that integrating financial technology significantly improves the efficiency and success of public institutions. It also improves customer access to services, leading to greater customer satisfaction.

Conclusion: Fintech is a key player in enhancing the efficiency of public institutions by simplifying procedures and improving service delivery. It increases operational efficiency and provides a user-friendly environment for citizens to interact with services.

Unique Contribution: This study provides valuable insights into the implementation of fintech in public institutions, contributing to the broader discussion on digital transformation in the public sector.

Key Recommendations: This research emphasises the need to expand digital financial facilities and highlights the importance of continuing to adopt financial technology to support progress in institutional performance.

Keywords: Financial Technology, Performance, Public Institutions, Financial Services, Jordan.

Introduction

Financial technology is regarded as one of the advances due to the strong link between information technology and the financial industry, two industries essential to economic development. The public service is also regarded as one of the most significant sectors in Jordan due to the support it receives from state policy. Many people rely on financial technology to both receive and provide services; as a result, services must be strengthened and linked to technological advancements, particularly those related to finance, in order to achieve financial inclusion and deliver outstanding performance that will enable significant change. According to Al-Amarnah et al. (2023), the integration of fintech solutions has improved risk management approaches. Furthermore, pressure from competitors and clients has a noteworthy positive impact on the adoption of fintech products, as seen in banks (Bani Atta, 2025).

Financial technology is crucial for enhancing the efficiency of public institutions in numerous ways. By switching to electronic processes, paperwork can be reduced or eliminated, transaction processing can be accelerated, and costs can be reduced. Additionally, the adoption of decentralised data registries and blockchain-based technologies can increase accountability and transparency in public bodies. As a result, financial transactions can be precisely monitored and validated, enhancing the public's experience with online financial services that facilitate contact between citizens and public agencies.

Fintech enables quick requests for financial transactions, payment of taxes, and delivery of innovative and cutting-edge public services, such as digital finance for small and medium-sized enterprises. While financial data can be studied using graphical analysis and artificial intelligence to detect odd patterns that indicate corruption or fraud, Fintech can be used to simplify financial regulatory procedures in government organisations, making them more straightforward to comprehend and more likely to be upheld. However, a few potential obstacles, such as security and privacy issues, as well as the obligation to provide public personnel with the necessary training and expertise to utilise this technology proficiently, may arise. With the objective to guarantee the achievement of the values of sustainable growth, this study seeks to shed light on one of the most important issues in the provision of services to the public, namely, financial technology, as well as the vital role it performs in promoting the performance of public institutions that provide the most efficient financial services. From here, based on the above, the question that comes to mind is whether the use of financial technology by public institutions has an impact on their performance. This is what the current study will try to answer by suggesting the following hypothesis:

H1: FinTech practices, as perceived by employees, have a statistically significant positive impact on the performance of public organisations in Jordan.

Literature Review

Fintech refers to the application of technological innovation in finance, encompassing entrepreneurs, technology, services, digitisation, business, new generation possibilities, products, or risks, according to a report by Subanidja et al. (2020). A process for creating, updating, or improving a business model is also described by the FinTech mechanism (Legowo et al., 2020). Additionally, according to Hamdoush et al. (2021), this term has expanded widely,

as it typically focuses on luring clients with services and products that are user-friendly, simple to use, more efficient, and transparent. Financial technology is also recognised to be related to the following four primary industries: credit and deposit, raising capital, clearing and settlement, and investments and wealth management (Al-Najjar, 2019).

The potential of financial technology to modernise and accelerate activities has transformed the banking industry as well as the national and international financial system (Vivek, 2021). Furthermore, Financial technology is described as "computer software and other technologies applied to support or enable banking and financial services; it is an economic sector that uses technology to improve the efficiency of financial services" by (Schueffel, 2016, p. 35). The Suryono et al. (2020) study verified that the advent of financial technology was caused by the growth in digital transformation, which was regarded as the most recent breakthrough in financial services. The study also showed that the financial technology research sector is still relatively young, as it offers a broad range of financial services, including finance, electronic trade, cryptocurrency, and others.

Career performance is the amount of mental and physical effort an individual exerts during a specific period of time, as well as the speed at which work is completed. Therefore, it is preferable to agree on the quantity and volume of work to achieve an appropriate rate of growth in performance, commensurate with the experience and capabilities the individual acquires. Accordingly, it is essential to understand the capabilities, motivations, and orientations of individuals to distribute work and tasks properly, i.e., place the right person in the proper position (Kurdi, 2019).

Digitising payments has a significant positive impact on public finance management tasks, such as making payments accurately and promptly, communicating with beneficiaries, improving financial and accounting reporting, and enhancing accountability through the creation of more reliable audit trails (Cangiano et al., 2019). Furthermore, transactions can be accelerated and government interactions with citizens facilitated, given its frequent use of the latest technologies and processes that offer innovative solutions to reinvent traditional information systems. Fintech implementation can also benefit social initiatives, including budgeting, treasury cash control, and money transfer operations (Una et al., 2023).

In its broadest sense, innovation refers to improved outcomes and altered decisions or operations that support an organization's capacity to acquire knowledge (Dodgson & Gann, 2018). Management of performance within public-sector organisations is perhaps one of the most important practices that can be employed to reduce system and employee inefficiencies and enhance overall organisational effectiveness. In actuality, effective performance management may not solely reduce resource loss and boost organisational effectiveness. Additionally, it may produce better results in terms of citizens' satisfaction with public performance (Ma, 2017). According to Jenatabadi (2015), efficiency, effectiveness, quality, productivity, quality of life, profitability, innovation, and learning can all be used to measure an organisation's performance.

Methodology

Study Sources

Using a research methodology to address the study variables is crucial. It aims to uncover their nature and the areas they cover, utilising previous publications, research, and studies. Many previous studies have highlighted this importance, such as Oreqat (2021) and Al-Muntasir (2022). A questionnaire was distributed to gather data and then to evaluate the data using the appropriate statistical methods.

Study Design

This study adopts a quantitative survey design to observe the impact of financial technology implementation on institutional performance. Data will be collected through a structured questionnaire aimed at employees across various departments. A random sample of participants will be designated to ensure unbiased representation. The survey focuses on the extent of financial technology practice and its perceived impact on effectiveness, transparency, and service quality. Data will be evaluated using statistical methods such as correlation and regression to explore the relationship between financial technology adoption and institutional performance.

Study Population and Sample

The study population consists of employees of the Greater Amman Municipality, which currently employs approximately 23,000 staff members, including administrative personnel, service workers, and other employees responsible for managing the city's large-scale municipal operations. The sample size was estimated at approximately 378 based on Krejcie and Morgan (1970). This represents a 95% confidence level, plus a 5% margin of error, which is a common approach in most social science research.

Study Tool

The questionnaire was chosen as the most suitable tool to meet the study's objectives, based on the data required and the methodology employed. It was divided into three sections: personal characteristics, fintech variables, and performance variables for public institutions. A Likert five-point scale was used to assess agreement levels. The questionnaire's reliability was ensured, meaning that results from a new sample would closely match those from the original. To confirm the validity of the data, previous studies such as Ahmed et al. (2023), Alghadi et al. (2024), and Taqa (2025) suggest that a group of experts have to review the instrument, which results in adjustments to achieve a better balance. Additionally, Cronbach's alpha was used to evaluate internal consistency and the validity of the responses.

The Cronbach's alpha coefficient has a high value of 0.894 for the measure of financial technology, 0.873 for the dimension of public institutions' Performance, and a total coefficient for the questionnaire of 0.861. It should be highlighted that every percentage was greater than the statistically acceptable percentage, which, according to Zeller (2005), is 60%, demonstrating the validity of the study tool. This indicates that the questionnaire is highly

reliable, and we can infer that if it had been administered again, it would have yielded identical outcomes for the same sample or category, demonstrating its ability to meet the study's objectives.

Study Model: The following study model was adopted: Financial Technology **IV**, Public institutions' Performance **DV** and Personal variables.

To achieve the study's objectives, 378 questionnaires were distributed, with 326 valid responses (86%). Descriptive statistics, including sample demographics, means, and standard deviations, were used. Additionally, hypothesis testing was conducted using correlation and regression analysis, with statistical software to analyse the data.

Data Analysis and Test of Hypothesis

In this section, the study's demographic factors are described.

Demographics of respondents

The results relevant to the personal study sample's data were presented and examined in terms of the following variables in order to satisfy this requirement: Sex, Age, Education, Years of Experience, and Job Level.

Table 1: The distribution of the sample according to the gender variable

Variable	Statement	Percentage %
Gender	Male	48
	Female	52
Age	Less than 30	18
	31-40	32
	41-50	34
	More than 50	16
Education	Less than Bachelor	31
	Bachelor	54
	post-graduate (Master and Doctorate)	15
Experience	5 or less	12
	6-10	38
	11-15	34
	16 or more	16
Job Level	Directorate Manager	17
	Department Manager	21
	Employee	62

According to gender, the highest percentage of the study sample fell into the female category (52%), while the proportion of males was 48%, as shown in Table 1 above. It has been observed that there are more female employees than male employees, likely due to the character of the

profession. Table 1 also displays the spread of the age variable. The age ranges from 31 to 40 years, followed by the age category from 30 to less than 30 years, and the age range from 41 to 50 years comprised a majority of the study's sample (34%), having an estimated rate of 16% for the final group from 50 to more than 50 years. These results indicate that 84% of the respondents are under the age of 50, suggesting that young individuals comprise the majority of the study population. As a result, the Amman Municipality is a significant institution that employs young people who are energetic and capable of handling pressure. The results in Table 2 above reveal that 54% of the sample holds a bachelor's degree, making them the largest group in the study sample. Third-placed postgraduate degrees were held by 15% of the study population, while fewer than a bachelor's degree were held by 31% of the sample. These results show that the municipality of Amman has significant university-level scientific competencies that can contribute to addition and development. These findings are understandable in light of the scientific qualifications required by public institutions in their various hiring processes. Regarding the factor "years of experience," according to Table 2, the category (6–10) came in first with a score of 38%, followed by the category (11–15 years) with a rate of 34%, the category (16 or more years) rated 16%, and the group (less than 5 years) with an estimated rate of 12%. Young individuals with university degrees are drawn to the institution because they reflect a positive energy that will help them grow as professionals and enhance their competencies. The study sample's workers with less than 16 years of experience make up the biggest percentage, with 84%. There are also a few people with substantial experience in the institutions who might be utilised in planning and development. Last but not least, the study sample's majority fell into the employee group, with an estimated rate of 62%, subsequently followed by the head of the department category, with an estimated rate of 21%, and the director's category, which came in third place and last with an estimated rate of 17%. To put it another way, it is a good thing that the study's focus was on organisation personnel because it meets the needs of this study.

Descriptive analysis of the study variables

This criterion provides basic information on how sample participants responded to the research variables. The study utilises the arithmetic mean and standard deviation to evaluate data dispersion, indicating how responses deviate from the mean. These measures were calculated to evaluate the financial technology status in the Greater Amman Municipality.

Table 2: Means and SDs of the elements of financial technology

S/N	Item	Mean	SD	Rank	Level
1	Greater Amman Municipality provides digital programs to its clients to facilitate their transactions	3.49	1.760	8	High
2	Greater Amman Municipality provides financial technology that	3.36	1.294	13	Medium

	contributes to the payment and collection of dues to and from the institution					
3	Greater Amman Municipality allows its smart programs to deal with individuals of all levels	3.61	1.165	4	High	
4	Greater Amman Municipality provides modern financial technology to attract its clients	3.78	1.274	2	High	
5	Dealing with financial technology by the Greater Amman Municipality guarantees speed of communication	3.51	1.382	7	High	
6	Dealing with financial technology accelerates the organization's operational pace	3.84	1.102	1	High	
7	Dealing with digitization by the institution contributes to reducing the burden of waiting and moving the customer to settle his transactions	3.72	1.407	3	High	
8	Greater Amman Municipality deals with digitization, allowing it to conduct many transactions with several parties at the same time.	3.46	1.319	10	High	
9	Greater Amman Municipality provides security to	3.48	1.248	9	High	

	its customers due to its dealings with digitization				
10	The institution's dealings with financial technology protects it from embezzlement	3.56	1.187	5	High
11	Dealing with financial technology enables the institution to ensure that the dues of its creditors are received	3.44	1.316	11	High
12	The institution deals with secure digital technologies	3.37	1.329	12	Medium
13	The institution's adoption of financial technology for payment gives it security and enhances the confidence of its clients	3.52	1.204	6	High
	Total	3.54	1.703		High

Table 2 shows the sample's responses to questions about the financial technology element. Item 6 was rated highest with a mean numerical value of 3.84 and a standard deviation of 1.102. This suggests that the majority of respondents think financial technology improves an organisation's efficiency. Respondents' second-place score of 3.78 and standard deviation of 1.274 for Item 4 indicate that they agree that Greater Amman Municipality draws customers by offering cutting-edge financial technologies. Item 7, which came in third place with a mean of 3.72 and an SD of 1.407, shows how the institution's use of digitisation lessens the anxiety associated with waiting for the consumer to complete their transactions.

Item 3, which ranks fourth, with a numerical mean of 3.61 and a standard deviation of 1.165, indicates that the Greater Amman Municipality enables its intelligent programs to serve individuals from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds. With a numerical mean of 3.56 and a standard deviation of 1.187, item 10 is ranked sixth, indicating that the organisation is protected from embezzlement through its use of financial technology. Item 13 in rank 6 has a high degree of agreement, a standard rating of 1.204, and an arithmetic mean of 3.52. It boosts the trust of its customers and gives the organisation security. The Greater Amman Municipality's use of financial technology guarantees speed of communication, according to item 5 from the seventh rank, which has an arithmetic mean of 3.51 and a standard score of 1.382. Moreover, Item 1 ranked eighth with a standard score of 1.760 and an arithmetic mean of 3.49, indicating that

the Greater Amman Municipality primarily provides digital programs to its customers to speed up their processes. Item 9 was ranked ninth in terms of importance and, through an arithmetical mean of 3.48 and a standard score of 1.248, provided significant support for the assertion that the Greater Amman Municipality provides security to its customers as a result of its contacts with digitisation.

By utilising digitisation, the Greater Amman Municipality can conduct multiple transactions with various parties simultaneously. This was corroborated by item 8, which ranked tenth with a numerical mean of 3.46 and a standard deviation of 1.319. Item 11, which ranked eleventh, showed that the institution can use financial technology to ensure that its creditors' debts are paid, given an arithmetic mean of 3.44 and a standard deviation of 1.316. According to Item 12, which ranked last in terms of relevance with an arithmetic mean of 3.37 and a standard deviation of 1.329, the study's subject, the Amman Municipality, addresses the safe use of digital technologies. Item 2, which states that the Greater Amman Municipality provides financial technology that facilitates the payment and collection of dues to and from the institution, received the lowest ranking on the list, with a modest degree of agreement, a mathematical mean of 3.36, and a standard score of 1.294. The overall arithmetic mean associated with this financial technology variable was 3.54, with a standard deviation of 1.703. The table shows that there is a high level of interest in the financial technology variable, with a high arithmetic mean obtained based on the replies of Amman municipality employees. This shows that the study sample as a whole agrees that there is a high degree of financial technology items.

Table 3: Means and SDs for the Public institutions' Performance

S/N	Item	Mean	SD	Rank	Level
1	Greater Amman Municipality seeks to provide high-quality services	3.51	1.332	9	High
2	Greater Amman Municipality is focusing on acquiring modern programs to improve the quality of public service	3.76	1.246	1	High
3	Greater Amman Municipality relies on the principle of continuous improvement	3.69	1.386	3	High

	and achieving distinguished quality in public service				
4	Greater Amman Municipality uses modern methods to control the quality of service	3.53	1.235	8	High
5	Greater Amman Municipality is interested in research and development in order to improve and innovate in its services	3.64	1.187	4	High
6	Greater Amman Municipality works to innovate its services based on its internal marketing	3.57	1.219	7	High
7	The institution is interested in employing efficient workers capable of creation and innovation	3.48	1.263	10	High
8	Greater Amman Municipality attaches sufficient importance to academic studies as coordinate for innovation	3.61	1.172	5	High
9	The worker within the organisation	3.47	1.257	11	High

	specialises in the job he occupies				
10	Greater Amman Municipality is achieving increased growth rates	3.71	0.934	2	High
11	Greater Amman Municipality pursues continuous improvement of the worker according to his position in the job	3.58	1.218	6	High
12	Greater Amman Municipality grants promotion and rewards to workers based on professional capabilities and talents	3.42	0.975	12	High
	Total	3.59	1.216		High

Table 3, which displays the sample's responses to the performance of public institutions variable, demonstrates that the Greater Amman Municipality is making a significant effort to acquire cutting-edge programs to enhance the standard of public service. Item 2's mean value was 3.76, and its standard deviation was 1.246. With an arithmetic mean of 3.71 and a standard deviation of 0.934, item 10—which most respondents in the sample strongly agreed that Greater Amman Municipality is experiencing rising growth rates—came in second. Third, the arithmetic mean and standard deviation of item 3 are both 3.69 and 1.386, respectively, suggesting an agreement that the Greater Amman Municipality adheres to the idea of continual improvement and strives for exceptional quality in public service.

Item 5 was ranked fourth, having an arithmetic mean of 3.64 and a standard deviation of 1.187, indicating an interest in research and development to enhance and innovate its services. At an arithmetic mean of 3.61, a standard deviation of 1.172, and an extensive level of consensus that the Amman Municipality gives academic research adequate emphasis as a foundation for innovation, Item 8 also came in fifth. Item 11 ranked sixth with an arithmetic mean of 3.58, a standard deviation of 1.218, and a high degree of agreement that the Amman Municipality supports workers' continuous development in line with their job roles.

Item 6 ranks seventh with an arithmetic mean of 3.57, a standard deviation of 1.219, and a fair degree of agreement that Amman Municipality attempts to reinvent its services based on internal marketing. Item 4, on the other hand, which is rated seventh, has a mean of 3.53, a standard deviation of 1.235, and a high degree of agreement that Amman Municipality employs cutting-edge techniques to manage service quality. Reviewing Item 1, which is ranked as the tenth most important, reveals that the sample's mean response value is 3.51 and its standard deviation is 1.332, demonstrating Amman Municipality's commitment to offering high-quality services.

Item 7, which expressed Amman Municipality's aim to harness creative and inventive human abilities, came in at number 10 at an arithmetic mean of 3.48 as well as a standard deviation of 1.263. Furthermore, Item 9 ranked eleventh and last with regard to the significance of the responses provided by the participants, at an arithmetic mean of 3.47 along with a standard deviation of 1.257. This suggests that Amman Municipality recognises the notion that each employee possesses a significant level of expertise in their respective role.

Item 12, which claimed that the Amman Municipality gives bonuses and promotions to staff members based on their professional skills and abilities, was ranked last by the respondents. Its standard deviation was 0.975, and its arithmetic mean was 3.42. With an overall mathematical mean of 3.59 and a standard deviation of 1.216, this financial performance indicator demonstrated that the sample's respondents agreed with it, indicating that the institution must strive for excellence.

Testing of the hypothesis- Correlation and Regression.

The link between the independent and dependent variables was ascertained using correlation coefficients, and the hypothesis was tested using the regression approach.

Table 4: Distribution of the sample according to the gender variable

Pearson Correlation	0.684
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.0000
N	326

Table 4 above shows that, with a correlation coefficient of 0.684, there is a significant positive direct relationship between the financial technology variable and financial success. The following table provides a summary of the regression approach used to determine how the independent variable affects the dependent variable.

Table 5: Results of regression analysis

**F-statistic = 17.594 Prob(F-statistic) = 0.0000 $\alpha =$
0.05**

Variable	Coefficient	S.Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Constant	1.003	0.342	3.963	0.000

Financial technology	0.618	0.385	2.937	0.000
R=	0.624			
R ² =	0.413			
S.E of Regression	= 0.369			

Only 41.3% of the changes in the dependent variable can be explained by the regression relationship, according to the coefficient of determination R^2 , a measure of the degree of fit; the remaining 58.7% are attributed to additional factors not considered in the model. Additionally, the F value's significance demonstrates how well the regression line and linear relationship fit the scatterplot's points. A statistically significant positive relationship between the two variables is also indicated by the regression coefficient value of 0.618 in Table 5. Any rise in financial technology by one unit increases the public Institutions' performance variable of 0.618 because a significant level of 0.0000, or less than 0.05, occurred. Due to the foregoing, it is reasonable to adopt the study hypothesis.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Even as financial technology offers numerous advantages for public institutions, innovation cannot be fostered at the expense of security, client privacy, and information security. Within this framework, financial technology vendors and regulators should strike a balance between the risk-aversion phenomenon and the global trend toward financial technology innovation. They should also make sure that new technological advancements do not pose a threat to financial stability by serving as instruments for fraud, theft, money laundering, and terrorist financing.

As it has become essential for public institutions to develop and maintain high levels of service performance and focus on quality, this always directs employees to provide service to a suitable standard on a continuous basis. This is because it is thought to be a primary goal to achieve favorable benefits like increased growth and continuity. This study sought to ascertain how financial technology practices impacted the efficacy of Jordanian public institutions.

This study finds a significant correlation between institutional performance and the use of financial technology (fintech), aligning with Uña et al. (2023), who highlighted fintech's positive effects on cash management, fiscal transparency, and budgeting. It also supports Zuliansyah et al. (2022), who found fintech improved ZIS management by increasing collections. The findings show that Greater Amman Municipality prioritises innovation in public services and is motivated to attract customers by simplifying online transactions. These results highlight the importance of fintech in enhancing public sector performance and customer engagement.

This study suggests that government institutions should enhance their use of financial technology (fintech) practices to improve performance and public services. It also recommends leveraging Amman Municipality's fintech experience to expand electronic financial services. The study advocates for Organizing forums to introduce fintech financing to other public institutions and allocating a yearly budget to support fintech initiatives, which would create

stable jobs and reduce unemployment. Further research is needed to fill gaps, explore new public institutions, and compare local and foreign samples.

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